

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

CREATING A TIME MACHINE

Antonov A.A.

Independent researcher

Ukraine

03142, Kiev, blvd. Vernadskogo 85, apt. 64

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824392>

Abstract

The article argues that the version of the special theory of relativity, which studied in all physics textbooks, is incorrect. And numerous proofs are given to it. SRT is refuted by the existence radio engineering, electrical engineering and computer technology. SRT is also refuted by the existence of shock oscillations and resonance. Consequently, to refute special theory of relativity it was not necessary to invent some very expensive experiments on Tevatron and Large Hadron Collider. And it was necessary simply to understand that the generally recognised version of special theory of relativity is refuted by numerous all known and therefore irrefutable natural and created by people processes. Therefore the author has created the corrected version of SRT, from which relativistic formulas and new scientific knowledge received after creation of incorrect version of special theory of relativity it followed that in the nature there is many other mutually invisible universes and antiuniverses. And besides existing in universes of matter, space and time, in antiuniverses there exist antimatter, anti-space and anti-time. And the existence of anti-time makes travelling not only in space but also in time possible. And the article explains how it can be done now.

Keywords: imaginary numbers; special theory of relativity, invisible universes and antiuniverses, portals, anomal zones

1. Introduction

The 20th century in physics turned out to be rich in new interesting scientific ideas. But many of them, even called theories, have not yet received experimental confirmation. For example, one of the most prominent and currently studied in all physics textbooks is the special theory of relativity (SRT) [1]-[3], which was nominated 66 times for the Nobel Prize, nevertheless, due to the lack of experimental confirmation, it has not received it.

And from the very beginning, the generally accepted version of SRT was criticised by Oliver Heaviside, Nikola Tesla, Nobel Prize winner Albert Abraham Michelson, Nobel Prize winner Wilhelm Frederick Ostwald, Nobel Prize winner Joseph John Thomson, Nobel Prize winner Svante August Arrhenius, Nobel Prize winner Philipp Eduard Anton von Lenard, Nobel Prize winner Alvar Gulstrand, Nobel Prize winner Wilhelm Carl Werner Otto Fritz Wien, Nobel Prize winner Walter Hermann Nernst, Nobel Prize winner Ernest Rutherford, Nobel Prize winner Johannes Stark, Nobel Prize winner Frederick Soddy, Nobel Prize winner Percy Williams Bridgman, Nobel Prize winner Edwin Mattison Macmillan, Nobel Prize winner Hideki Yukawa, Nobel Prize winner Hannes Olof Jösta Alven and many other distinguished scientists.

And in the XXI century this wrong version of STO was even by the above-mentioned arguments experimentally refuted [4]-[37] in the most indisputable way. However being unable to object, the authors of existing physics textbooks simply ignored these refutations and the incorrect version of SRT still continues to be taught even in the most prestigious universities in all countries.

All modern science is in a similar state. In the 21st century Jean de Climont in his books [34]-[37] writes about 9671 scientists who refuted the currently recognised scientific truths in all sciences. But the trouble is not that one or another infidelity has been discovered in the modern sciences. The author of the concept of 'open society' Sir Karl Raimund Popper, a member of the Royal Society of London, wrote [38]: "*...the struggle of opinions in scientific theories is inevitable and is a necessary condition for the development of science*". From which he made, at first glance paradoxical, but in fact correct conclusion that the most valuable results of scientific research are precisely the refutations of generally recognised theories, because they allow them to develop. And this is inevitable. There is no doubt that all scientific knowledge in a thousand years, much less in a million or a billion years, will be quite different. Therefore, we should not naively assume that we have already learnt everything and hinder the research of colleagues who propose new ideas.

2. The version of the special theory of relativity taught in all physics textbooks is incorrect

So what are the refutations of the generally recognised version of SRT obtained during the last century? They are the following:

- the relativistic formulas obtained in this SRT are incorrect;
- the relativistic formulas received in this SRT are incorrectly explained with use of incorrect principle of non-exceeding of speed of light;

• from relativistic formulas of this SRT wrong conclusions about physical unreality of imaginary numbers and existence in the nature of our only visible universe are made.

And these conclusions are available for experimental verification. Indeed, the relativistic formulae

$$m(v) = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \tag{1}$$

$$\Delta t(v) = \Delta t_0 \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \tag{2}$$

$$l(v) = l_0 \sqrt{1 - (v/c)^2} \tag{3}$$

Fig. 1. Graphs of functions $m(v)$, $\Delta t(v)$ and $l(v)$ corresponding to the existing versions of the STR in the subluminal $v < c$ and superluminal $v > c$ ranges

- where m_0 is the rest mass of a moving body;
- m is relativistic mass of a moving body;
- Δt_0 is rest time of a moving body;
- Δt is relativistic time of a moving body;
- l_0 is rest length of a moving body;
- l is relativistic length of a moving body;
- v is the velocity of the moving body;
- c is speed of light;

are explainable (see Fig. 1a,b,c) only in the range of pre-light velocities $v < c$, in which the values m , and l take values measured by real numbers. And in the range of superluminal velocities $v > c$ these quantities m , and l already take values measured by imaginary num-

bers discovered 500 years ago [39],[40], but still unexplained. After all, what is, for example, 10 grams, 20 seconds and 30 metres, everyone can explain, but what is $10i$ grams, $20i$ seconds and $30i$ metres, where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, is not explained in any textbook. Moreover, the graph in Fig. 1a in the range of velocities $v > c$ corresponds to a physically unstable process, which cannot exist in nature at all.

And since such a theory, the formulas of which even its creators could not explain, would be of no use to anyone, a postulate called the principle of not exceeding the speed of light was introduced into it. From this postulate it followed that imaginary numbers are physically unreal. Therefore, it was concluded that there was no need to explain them.

Fig. 2. In any radio engineering laboratory there are devices called frequency characteristic meters, which by their very existence prove the physical reality of imaginary and complex frequencies, and consequently, of any imaginary and complex numbers.

But there are other sciences besides physics. And in the theory of linear electric circuits used in radio engineering, electrical engineering and computer technology, according to Ohm's law as interpreted by Charles Proteus Steinmetz [41], there are imaginary resistances of capacitors and inductors (also called inductance coils), which are measured by devices available in any radio engineering laboratory (Fig. 2). This proves [42]-[53] that imaginary numbers are physically real⁵ and the principle of non-exceeding the speed of light is incorrect. And therefore relativistic formulas (1)-(3) are incorrect⁶.

3. Corrected version of the special theory of relativity

But even from the uncorrected relativistic formulas (1)-(3) follows an important conclusion, which the authors of SRT have overlooked and by their principle of non-exceeding of the speed of light have made this conclusion impossible – the velocity v in these formulas is an additional, besides length, width and height, spatial dimension.

Therefore in the corrected version of SRT the corrected relativistic formulas [54]-[61] are received

$$m(q, r, s) = \frac{m_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s}{\sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta t(q, r, s) = \Delta t_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2} \quad (5)$$

$$l(q, r, s) = l_0 i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s \sqrt{1 - [v/c - (q + r + s)]^2} \quad (6)$$

where $q(v) = [v_q/c]$ – is the "floor" function of discrete mathematics from the

argument v/c , which is the fourth spatial dimension (Fig. 3);

$r(v) = [v_r/c]$ – is the "floor" function of discrete maths from the argument v/c , being the fifth spatial dimension (Fig. 3);

$s(v) = [v_s/c]$ – is the "floor" function of discrete maths from the argument v/c , being the sixth spatial dimension (Fig. 3);

v_q, v_r, v_s – projections of the velocity vector v on orthogonal coordinates q, r, s (see Fig. 4).

Fig 3. Graphs of functions $q(v), r(v), s(v)$ illustrating the meaning of the "floor" function of discrete mathematics

From them it follows that we live in a Multiverse [62]-[77], which is six-dimensional – three dimensions x, y, z has each universe and three more dimensions q, r, s are coordinates of universes in the Multiverse (Fig. 4) – and is described by quaternions $f_{q,r,s}(x, y, z) +$

$i_1q + i_2r + i_3s$, the number of which is equal to the number of universes in the Multiverse. This is exactly what Lisa Randall predicted: "We could be living in a three-dimensional pocket of higher dimensional space."

Fig. 4. Six-dimensional space of the hidden Multiverse, where q, r, s are the coordinates of invisible parallel universes, and x, y, z are the coordinates of the matter content in each parallel universe

⁵ Since you can only measure what actually physically exists.

⁶ Since the derivation of correct relativistic formulas due to absence in the 20th century of necessary experimental and theoretical knowledge simply was not completed.

$$i_1^2 = i_2^2 = i_3^2 = -1 \tag{7}$$

$$i_1 i_2 i_3 = i_2 i_3 i_1 = i_3 i_1 i_2 = -1 \tag{8}$$

$$i_1 i_3 i_2 = i_2 i_1 i_3 = i_3 i_2 i_1 = 1 \tag{9}$$

In the mathematics of hypercomplex numbers, the function $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s$ can be calculated only for integer values⁷ q, r, s , but can take both positive and negative values, as well as both real and imaginary values. But

we have already proven that imaginary numbers are physically real. Therefore, we must also explain them. Therefore, let us now consider the values of the quantities $m(v)$, $\Delta t(v)$ and $l(v)$, and in the range of velocities $v > c$ for successive values of the argument $q + r + s$ equal to 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, ... Then for our visible universe with coordinates $q = 0, r = 0, s = 0$, i.e. located at we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -1$. This situation also corresponds to an invisible universe, since it is located beyond the event

Fig. 5. Possible version of the quaternion structure of the hidden Multiverse

horizon. We will call it a tardyon⁸ antiuniverse. For the value $q + r + s = 3$ in the velocity range $v > c$ we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = -i$. This situation corresponds to an invisible universe, since it is also located beyond the event horizon. We will call it a tachyon⁹ antiuniverse. For the value $q + r + s = 4$ in the velocity range $v > c$ we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = +1$. This situation corresponds to an invisible tardyon universe (but a different one), since it is also located beyond the event horizon. For the value

$q + r + s = 5$ in the velocity range $v > c$ we get $i_1^q i_2^r i_3^s = +i$. This situation corresponds to an invisible tachyon universe (but a different one), since it is also located beyond the event horizon. Thus, all universes are mutually invisible. Therefore, we will call our Multiverse hidden. And to make sure that invisible universes and antiuniverses neighbouring our visible universe exist, one can try to see them [79]-[84] from portals, the entrances to which are probably more than two hundred thousand so-called anomalous zones [85]-[88] existing

⁷ And for non-integer values of the argument q the author obtained [78] the formula $i^q = \cos(q\pi/2) + i\sin(q\pi/2)$. It, in particular, will be needed in mathematical processing of experimental data of geophysical investigations of portals

⁸ The term tardyon-universe was proposed by Isaac Asimov in short story "Take a match".

⁹ The term tachyon-universe was proposed by Isaac Asimov in short story "Take a match".

on Earth. People avoid visiting them - and rightly so – as the portals are invisible labyrinths, once in which it is almost impossible to get out of them. These portals are analogous to a corridor in your flat, from which you can look into the next room and see something in it. And to make sure that you really see something about the neighbouring universe in the portal, you should look at the starry sky through a telescope and see that

the constellations on it are at least a little bit different from those outside the portals.

In other words, it is necessary to do an experiment similar to the famous experiment of Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington in 1919 [89] by which he confirmed the prediction of the general theory of relativity about the deflection of light rays in the Sun's gravitational field.

Fig. 6. Scheme of an astronomical experiment to detect invisible universes

And we're in luck. Since there are many anomalous zones on Earth, some of them may already host astronomical observatories, through whose telescope one can see these traces of the invisible out-of-portal neighbouring universe or antiuniverse. Such, for example, is the Main Astronomical Observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, which is located in the Golosevsky forest 12 km from the centre of the capital of Ukraine, Kiev. But since in the anomalous zone, i.e. at the very edge of the portal, the differences of the constellations observed by neighbouring observatories located in anomalous zone and outside the anomalous zone are very small and may be not visible to the naked eye, it is necessary to compare the observations of these observatories on the computer (Fig.6). And if these differences turn out to be too small, the telescope will have to be moved deeper into the portal. After all, Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington moved the telescope much further away – from England to the island of Principe in the Atlantic Ocean in order to perform his famous experiment.

4. Time Travels

As is easy to notice, in Fig. 5 half of the universes of the hidden Multiverse are called antiuniverses in order to draw the readers' attention to the fact that they are cosmic antipodes of other universes. For them, the quantities $m(v)$, $\Delta t(v)$, $l(v)$ in formulas (4)-(6) differ only in sign. That is, the concepts of matter, time and space in the universes correspond to the concepts of antimatter, anti-time and anti-space in the antiuniverses [90]-[93]. But, as on Earth, inhabitants-antipode in space do not notice this difference, since the same physical, chemical, biological and other natural scientific laws operate in the universes and antiuniverses.

And when observed from Earth, in all universes and anti-universes, as they move away from our visible universe, not only the distance increases, but also time (like in time zones on Earth). Moreover, in universes it becomes greater than on Earth, and in anti-universes it becomes less than on Earth. And this circumstance

makes time travel really possible both in the past and in the future.

Here are a couple of quotes that explain the current state of understanding of this problem. *“Time is the most frequently used word in the English language and the third most frequently used word in Russian. It is in every other language, too, because synchronizing actions in time is just as important as coordinating them in space. Without knowing the exact time, it is impossible to organize your life and plan it in advance. If in ancient times you could rely on natural cycles and an internal sense of time, then in our days you need to constantly have a watch or a phone with you. Time is the most important of the abstract concepts that we pronounce every day. Every thinking person has thought about the problem of time at least once in his life, and a huge amount of philosophical and scientific literature has been written on this topic. Nevertheless, no one can say for sure what time is.”* [94]

Here is what Stephen William Hawking writes about this: *“In everyday life, there is a huge difference between moving forward and backward in time. Imagine that a cup of water falls from a table and breaks into pieces. If you film this fall, then when you watch the film, it will immediately become clear whether the film is running forward or backward. If it is running backward, then we will see how the fragments lying on the floor suddenly come together and, having formed a whole cup, jump onto the table. And you will be able to say that the film was running backward, because in everyday life this does not happen. Otherwise, the faience factories would have to be closed”* [95].

This phenomenon, known as the arrow of time, is one of the most amazing problems in physics. And the name “arrow of time” was proposed by the British physicist Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington at the beginning of the 20th century [96]. And all our life experience, it would seem, confirms this opinion.

The corrected version of the STR, in which the new concept of ‘anti-time’ has appeared, allows this life experience to be corrected. Indeed, if we assume that

one day travel through the vastness of the hidden Multiverse will become possible for people on Earth, then time travel [97] will also become possible, both in the past and in the future. Let us show this.

But first, let us explain what we need to learn to do for this. And the main thing we need to learn is to master portals [98], [99], i.e. understand what they are and learn to navigate in them. Just as people once learned to navigate with a compass in the boundless expanses of the seas and oceans. Or even in the forest, in the desert, in the mountains, in any unfamiliar area. Even in labyrinths. So, a portal is an unfamiliar area that has become an invisible labyrinth for people. Portals are transitions from one universe to another, which turn these universes into communicating vessels. Therefore, at the entrance and exit of portals, according to the law of communicating vessels, the habitat should be almost the same – the same air, the same water, the same vegetation and animals¹⁰. Only the area is unfamiliar. But in order not to get lost in the portals and find the way back, you can use, as in mythology, the ‘thread of Ariadne’. Or, in order not to risk ourselves, we can send unmanned vehicles to explore the portals, which people have now learned to make very well. It is also not difficult to create something like a radio compass, taking into account that as you dive into the portals, the electromagnetic field intensity from earthly radio stations should decrease. And on the way back, it should increase. Having got through the portal to some other planet, in order to move further in the hidden Multiverse, you will need to use unmanned aerial vehicles to search for anomalous zones on it, which are entrances to portals that lead to other neighboring universes. And so on. But all these problems are quite solvable.

And now we will show that the concept of the ‘arrow of time’ in the corrected version of STR is already partially refutable, since although we will not restore the cup mentioned by Hawking, we will be able to move into the past and future time. For this, we will use Fig. 7 and 8. In them, the positive branch of the vertical coordinate axis corresponds to time t , measured in tar-

dion (including our visible tardyon) universes by positive real numbers, and its negative branch corresponds to negative time t in tardyon antiuniverses. Similarly, the positive branch of the horizontal coordinate axis corresponds to positive imaginary time¹¹ it , measured in tachyon universes by positive imaginary numbers, and its negative branch corresponds to negative time it in tachyon antiuniverses. On the vertical axis of real time t and on the horizontal axis of imaginary time it , thick black arrows show our comparatively long-term activity in tardyon and tachyon universes and anti-universes. And thin красными и синими стрелками показаны red and blue arrows show transitions through portals (staying in which is short-lived) between neighboring universes and antiuniverses.

Then we will consider the simplest options for traveling to the future and the past, since they would be very useful to us. Indeed, traveling to the future would allow us to refuse to continue all types of our unsuccessful activities and make them much more effective. But after such a search for the most effective option for activity, it will be necessary to return to the original state in order to start doing something differently and to do this. Traveling to the past would also be useful if, despite the search for an acceptable option for subsequent activity, it still turned out to be bad. Then it would be necessary, again having returned to the past, to somehow correct it. Therefore, having received the opportunity to travel through time, people could make their lives much more successful and happier. And since such searches for happiness are often a rather intimate activity, it would obviously be useful to begin them with the transition from our tardyon universe through the necessary portal to one of the neighboring tachyon universes or antiuniverses, since our activity in them is not visible from our tardyon universe due to the fact that time in them flows in mutually perpendicular directions¹². And we will have to move to the tachyon universe if we are interested in something in the future. And we will have to move to the tachyon antiuniverse if we need to do something in the past.

Fig. 7. Possible route of travel to the past time

¹⁰ And if at least one portal on Earth ended in open space, then there would have been no air, no water, no anything else on Earth, like on the Moon or Mars.

¹¹ Despite the fact that the physical reality of imaginary numbers is denied in the generally accepted version of SRT, the term ‘imaginary time’ is used in modern physics. For example, in [95] Hawking writes: “Attempts to unify gravity with

quantum mechanics have led to the concept of imaginary time”.

¹² On the essence of imaginary time, Hawking holds the same opinion: “Imaginary time is a new dimension at right angles to ordinary real time” [95].

it was proved that the speed v gives rise to three additional spatial dimensions;

- it was found out that there exists in Nature a six-dimensional Multiverse containing about twenty mutually invisible three-dimensional universes and antiuniverses, whose position in the Multiverse space is determined by three additional dimensions.

It is explained that antimatter in the Multiverse is located in the antiuniverses, which are antipodes of other universes. In the same antiuniverses there are an anti-time, which is opposite to time of other universes. Examples of use of this anti-time are given, allowing already now to move both in the past and in the future time. And the existence of anti-time corrects the understanding of the phenomenon 'arrow of time'.

But anomalous zones in different countries on Earth may have different service advantages and disadvantages. Therefore, different countries may use different portals and different time travelling routes using them. And it will allow to get more valuable information about portals. Astro-geophysical researches of portals [99]-[115] made as a result of such time-travelling in our hidden Multiverse will allow to create time machines imitating on the Earth stay of people in portals. And this will significantly increase the effectiveness of scientific research and the corresponding accelerated intellectual and economic development of our entire human civilisation.

Acknowledgments

The author sincerely thanks his wife Olga Ilyinichna Antonova for her participation in the discussion, understanding and valuable advice, with whose support he also wrote the book "*Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity*". And for its publication he is now looking for a sponsor and publisher.

References:

1. Einstein A. (1920). Relativity: The Special and General Theory. H. Holt and Company. NY.
2. Bohm D. (2006). The Special Theory of Relativity. Routledge, Abingdon on Thames.
3. Penrose R. (2010). The Nature of Space and Time. Princeton University Press. Princeton.
4. Antonov A.A. (2021). The special theory of relativity stated in physics text-books is incorrect. 77th International Scientific Conference of the Eurasian Scientific Association. "Theoretical and practical issues of modern science". Moscow. ESA. 11-15
5. Antonov A. A. (2021). Version of the special theory of relativity that is studied in all physics textbooks is incorrect. Österreichisches Multiscience Journal (Innsbruck, Austria). 43(1). 17-22. <http://osterr-science.com>
6. Antonov A. A. (2021). Generally accepted version of the special theory of relativity contained in physics textbooks is incorrect. The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 73(2). 39-43. DOI: 19.24412/9215-0365-2021-73-2-39-43
7. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity, which is studied in physics text-books, is incorrect. German International Journal of Modern Science. 16, 49-53. DOI: 10.24412/2701-8369-2021-16-49-53
8. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity, which is studied in all physics textbooks, is incorrect. Danish Scientific Journal. 51(1). 31-35. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
9. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity taught in all physics text-books is incorrect. Annali d'Italia. 22(1). 39-44. <https://www.anditalia.com/>
10. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity presented in physics text-books is wrong. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science 68(1). 3-7. DOI: 10.24412/3453-9875-2021-68-3-7.
11. Antonov A. A. (2021). In all physics textbooks an erroneous version of special theory of relativity is given. International independent scientific journal. 31.34-39. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
12. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity taught in physics textbooks is wrong. Journal of science. Lyon. 23. 47-52. <https://www.joslyon.com/>
13. Antonov A. A. (2021). All physics textbooks study incorrect special theory of relativity. Sciences of Europe. (Praha, Czech Republic) 79(1). 30-35. DOI: 10/24412/3162-2364-2021-79-30-35
14. Antonov A. A. (2021). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is incorrect because it denies the existence of radio engineering. 82nd International Scientific Conference of the Eurasian Scientific Association "Scientific result in theory and practice". Moscow. ESA. 11-15. <https://esa-conference.ru/sborniki/?y=2021>
15. Antonov A. A. (2022). The version of STR presented in physics textbooks is incorrect, since it follows from it that radio engineering should not exist. European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Science and Education. UK. 10(1). 440-445. DOI://doi.org/10.14738/aivp.101.2022
16. Antonov A. A. (2022). The existence of radio engineering refutes the physics text-books version of STR. The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 83(1). 19-22. DOI: 10.24412/9215-0365-2022-83-1-19-22
17. Antonov A.A. (2022). The fundamental Ohm's law in radio engineering as interpreted by Steinmetz, which proves the physical reality on imaginary ca-pacitive and inductive reactances, refuted the version of the STR presented in physics textbooks even before its creation. German International Journal of Modern Science. 26. 50-53. DOI: 10.24412/2701-8369-2022-26-50-63
18. Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is refuted by the existence of radio engineering. Danish Scientific Journal. 56. 56-59. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
19. Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR presented in physics textbooks is incorrect because it denies the possibility of the existence of Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz and, consequently, the existence of radio engineering. Annali d'Italia. 28(1), 43-47. <https://www.anditalia.com/>
20. Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is refuted by the existence of radio engineering. Norwegian Journal of develop-

ment of the International Science. 78(1). 63-67. DOI: 10.24412/3453-9875-2022-78-63-66.

21. Antonov A.A. (2022). If the physics textbook version of STR were true, then Ohm's law should not exist in nature, and therefore all radio engineering would not exist. *International independent scientific journal*. 36. 16-19. <http://www.iis-journal.com>

22. Antonov A.A. (2022). If the version of STR in physics textbooks were true, then there would be no radar, no television, no radio navigation, no telecommunication and many other things. *Journal of science. Lyon*. 28. 76-79. <https://www.joslyon.com/>

23. Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR set out in physics textbooks is in-correct because it states that Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz does not really exist, and therefore radio engineering does not exist either. *Sciences of Europe (Prague, Czech Republic)*. 87(1). 54-57. DOI: 10.24412/3162-2364-2022-1-54-57

24. Antonov A.A. (2022). Why the physics textbooks teach an incorrect version of the special theory of relativity which denies the existence of radio- and electrical engineering. III international scientific conference "Challenges and problems of modern science". London. Great Britain. 78-86. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486814>

25. Antonov A. A. (2023). Why is the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity being studied in physics textbooks, refuted the existence of radio- and electrical engineering even before its creation? The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 105. 83-89. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7560145

26. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is an incorrect version of the special theory of relativity that denies the possibility of the existence radio and electrical engineering being studied in physics textbooks? *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 48. 23-29. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7541137>

27. Antonov A.A. (2023). Who needs the incorrect version of special relativity taught in physics textbooks despite all its experimental refutations? *Annali d'Italia*. 39, 64-70. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7568916

28. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special theory of relativity that denies the possibility of the existence of radio and electrical engineering being studied in textbooks of physics? *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 100. 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528512>

29. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special theory of relativity, refuted by the existence of radio and electrical engineering, is still studied in all university physics textbooks? *Danish Scientific Journal*. 69. 66-72. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692053>

30. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special relativity still being studied in physics textbooks, which denies Ohm's law for alternating current used worldwide by millions of radio- and electrical engineers? *International independent scientific journal*. 46. 38-44. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525751>.

31. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is the generally accepted version of STR, which denies the possibility

of the existence of radio engineering and electrical engineering, tsunamis and bell ringing, the physical phenomenon of resonance and Ohm's physical law for alternating current, music created by the piano and even swing swings on the playground, nevertheless is still considered correct and studied in physics textbooks? *Sciences of Europe (Prague, Czech Republic)*. 112. 44-50. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7708515

32. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity still being studied in physics textbooks, despite all its experimental refutations. *European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Science and Education*. UK. 11(2). 61-71. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14738/aivp.112.14128>

33. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity, which denies the possibility of the existence of radio engineering and electrical engineering, has not yet been refuted. *Journal of science. Lyon*. 40. 19-25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704392>

34. Jean de Climont. (2009), (2010), (2016), (2020), (2023). *The Failure of Pure Science*. Editions d'Assailly.

35. Jean de Climont. (2017). *The alternative theories*. Editions d'Assailly.

36. Jean de Climont. (2019), (2020), (2023). *The Worldwide List of Alternative Theories and Critic*. Editions d'Assailly.

37. Jean de Climont. (2023). *Einstein and Maxwell speculation*. Editions d'Assailly.

38. Popper K.R. 2002. *Conjectures and Refutations. The Growth of Scientific Knowledge*. Routledge. London.

39. Weinstein E.W. (2005). *The CRC Concise Encyclopedia of Mathematics*. 3-rd ed. CRS Press. Boca Raton. FL.

40. Beckmann P. (1976). *A history of π* . 3rd edition. St. Martin Press. NY.

41. Steinmetz C. P. (2010). *Theory and Calculation of Electric Circuit*. Nabu Press.

42. Antonov A. A. (2008). Physical Reality of Resonance on Complex Frequencies. *European Journal of Scientific Research*. 21(4). 627-641.

<http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>

43. Antonov A. A. (2009). Resonance on Real and Complex Frequencies. *European Journal of Scientific Research*. 28(2). 193-204.

<http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>

44. Antonov A. A. (2010). New Interpretation of Resonance. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences and Technology*. 1(2). 1-12.

http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2010-888

45. Antonov A. A. (2010). Oscillation processes as a tool of physics cognition. *American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*. 1(2). 342-349. doi:10.5251/ajsir.2010.1.2.342.349

46. Antonov A. A. (2010). Solution of algebraic quadratic equations taking into account transitional processes in oscillation systems. *General Mathematics Notes*. 1(9). 11-16.

http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2010-887

47. Antonov A. A. (2013). Physical Reality of Complex Numbers. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 3(4). 219-230. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2013-898
48. Antonov A. A. (2014). Correction of the special theory of relativity: physical reality and nature of imaginary and complex numbers. *American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*, 5(2). 40-52. doi:10.5251/ajsir.2014.5.2.40.52
49. Antonov A. A. (2015). Physical reality of complex numbers is proved by research of resonance. *General Mathematics Notes*, 31(2). 34-53. http://www.emis.de/journals/GMN/yahoo_site_admin/assets/docs/4_GMN9212-V31N2.129701.pdf
50. Antonov A.A. (2015). Principle of physical reality of imaginary and complex numbers in modern cosmology: the nature of dark matter and dark energy. *Journal of the Russian physico-chemical society*, 87(1). 328-355. (In Russian) http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2015-1119
51. Antonov A. A. (2016). Physical Reality and Nature of Imaginary, Complex and Hypercomplex Numbers. *General Mathematics Notes*, 35(2). 40-63. http://www.geman.in/yahoo_site_admin/assets/docs/4_GMN-10932-V35N2.31895146.pdf
52. Antonov A. A. (2017). The physical reality and essence of imaginary numbers. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*, 6. 50-63. <http://www.njd-iscience.com>
53. Antonov A. A. (2018). Physical Reality and Essence of Imaginary Numbers in Astrophysics: Dark Matter, Dark Energy, Dark Space. *Natural Science*, 10(1). 11-30. doi:10.4236/ns.2018.101002
54. Antonov A.A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Science and Education*, UK, 11(5). 68-83. DOI:10.14738/aivp.115.15474
55. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected special theory of relativity. *Journal of science. Lyon*, 48. 27-36. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277156>
56. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected special theory of relativity. *Annali d'Italia*, 49, 25-35. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10214679
57. Antonov A. A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 123. 72-81,
58. Antonov A. A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*, 118. 40-49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10009500>
59. Antonov A. A. (2023). Alternative Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Sciences of Europe*. (Praha, Czech Republic). 128. 62-71.
60. Antonov A. A. (2023). Special Theory of Relativity. *German International Journal of Modern Science*, 67. 64-73. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10966458
61. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Danish Scientific Journal*, 77. 88-97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054677>
62. Antonov A. A. (2011), Structure of the Multiverse. *British Journal of Science*, 2(2). 51-60. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2011892
63. Antonov A. A. (2012). Multiverse. Time Travels. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences and Technology*, 12(2). 43-56. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2012-896
64. Antonov A.A. (2012). Discovery of the real Multiverse. *Encyclopaedia of Russian thought, Papers to the Russian Physical Society*, 16(3). 3-20. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2012-1115
65. Antonov A.A. (2013). Cognition of the Multiverse as a factor in accelerating the development of human civilisation. *Journal of Russian physical thought*, 1-12, 6-77. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2011-1117
66. Antonov A. A. (2015). Hidden Multiverse. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science*, 2(1). 25-32. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2015-903.
67. Antonov A.A. (2015). The astrophysical phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy proves the existence of the hidden Multiverse. *American Journal of Modern Physics*, 4(4). 180-188. doi: 10.11648/j.jamp.20150404.14
68. Antonov A. A. (2015). Why dark matter and dark energy are invisible? *Optics*, 4(6), 43-47. doi: 10.11648/j.optics.20150406.12
69. Antonov A. A. (2015). Hidden Multiverse: explanation of dark matter and dark energy phenomena. *International Journal of Physics*, 3(2). 84-87. doi:10.12691/ijp-3-2-6
70. Antonov A. A. (2015). Principles and structure of the real Multiverse: explanation of dark matter and dark energy phenomena. *American Journal of Modern Physics*, 4(1). 1-9. doi:10.11648/j.ajmp.20150401.11
71. Antonov A. A. (2015). Explanation of dark matter and dark energy phenomena. *Journal of Science Frontier Research: A Physics and Space Science*, 15(1). 33-38. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2015-902
72. Antonov A. A. (2015). Review of publications by A. A. Antonov on the problem of explaining the phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy. *Journal of the Russian physico-chemical society*, 87(3). 63-76.
73. Antonov A. A. (2016). Explaining the Phenomenon of Dark Matter and Dark Energy by Existence of the Hidden Multiverse. *Frontiers of Astronomy, Astrophysics and Cosmology*, 2(1). 1-9. doi: 10.12691/faac-2-1-1
74. Antonov A. A. (2016). What Physical World do We Live in? *Journal of Modern Physics*, 7(14). 1933-1943 <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jmp.2016.714170>
75. Antonov A. A. (2016). Hypothesis of the Hidden Multiverse: Explains Dark Matter and Dark Energy. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 7(10), 1228-1246. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2016.710111
76. Antonov A. A. (2017). Nature of dark matter and dark energy. *Journal of Modern Physics*, 8(4). 567-582. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2017.84038

77. Antonov A. A. (2017). Hypothesis of the hidden Multiverse explains the phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy. *Applied Physics Research*. 9(2). 30-41.
doi: <https://doi.org/10.5539/apr.v9n2p30>
78. Antonov A. A. (2024). Mathematical Sciences: From the Experimentally Proved Principle of the Physical Reality of Imaginary Numbers it Follows that the Invisible Afterlife World, Mentioned in All Religions, Really Exists. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*, 12(5). 119-145. DOI:10.14738/aivp.125.17569.
79. Antonov A. A. (2020). How to See Invisible Universes. *Journal of Modern Physics*. 11(05), 593-607. DOI: 10.4236/jmp.2020.115039
80. Antonov A. A. (2020). Can invisible universes be seen? *International independent scientific journal*. 21(2). 51-60. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
81. Antonov A. A. (2020), How to discover invisible universes. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 42(1). 36-48. <http://www.njd-iscience.com>
82. Antonov A. A. (2020). Universes Being Invisible on Earth outside the Portals Are Visible in Portals. *Natural Science*. 12(8). 569-587.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/ns.2020.128044>
83. Antonov A. A. (2020). Invisible universes can be seen in anomalous zones. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 43(1). 9-24. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
84. Antonov A. A. (2021). Invisible universes can be seen in anomalous zones. *International independent scientific journal*. 23(1). 28-44.
85. Chernobrov, V. (2000). *Encyclopedia of mysterious places of the Earth*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow.
86. Chernobrov, V. (2004). *Encyclopedia of mysterious places of Russia*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow.
87. Chernobrov, V. (2007). *Encyclopedia of mysterious places of Earth and space*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow.
88. Chernobrov, V. (2009). *Encyclopedia of mysterious places of Moscow and Moscow region*. Helios ARV. Moscow.
89. Dyson F.W, Eddington A.S., Davidson C. (1929). A determination of the deflection of light by the sun's gravitational field, from observations made at the total eclipse of May 29, 1919. *Philosophical transactions of the Royal Society A*. 220. 291-333. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.1920.0009>
90. Frazer G. (2004). *Antimatter: The Ultimate Mirror*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
91. Santilli R. M. (2006). *Isodual Theory of Antimatter: With Applications to Antigravity, Grand Unification and Cosmology*. Springer. Dordrecht. Netherlands.
92. Alain M., Le Brun V. (2012). *Matter, Dark Matter, and Anti-Matter: In Search of the Hidden Universe*. Springer-Verlag. NY.
93. Antonov A.A. (2016). Dark matter, dark energy and antimatter are located in the hidden Multiverse. *PONTE*. 72(8). 288-300.
94. Dionis Dimetor. The arrow of time, Loschmidt's demon and quantum thermodynamics. Why is time irreversible? <https://habr.com/ru/articles/785014/>
95. Hawking S.W. (1988). *Brief History of Time: From the Big Bang to Black Holes*. Bantam Dell Publishing Group. UK.
96. Eddington, A. S. (1928). *Nature of the Physical World*. Cambridge University Press, London
97. Chernobrov, V. (1999). *Secrets of Time*. Helios ARV. Moscow.
98. Antonov A. A. (2012), Earth, portals, parallel universes. *American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*. 3(6). 464-473.
doi:10.5251/ajsir.2012.3.6.464.473
99. Antonov A. A. (13 January 2016). How Portals of the Invisible Multiverse Operate. *Science PG Frontiers*.
<http://www.sciencepublishinggroup.com/news/sciencepgfrontiersinfo?articleid=7>
100. Antonov A.A Geophysical exploration of portals will provide new knowledge about space. *Proceedings of the III International Scientific Conference*. Philadelphia. USA. "The modern vector of the development of science". Philadelphia, USA. 2023. 85-101. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7709801>
101. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to discover invisible universes and to explore them. *European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Sciences and education*. UK. 11(2). 370-391.
DOI:10.14738/aivp.112.14323.
102. Antonov A.A. 2023. The necessity of geophysical researches of portals. *The scientific heritage*. (Budapest, Hungary). 110. 77-90.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7804563
103. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to prove the existence of invisible universes and to explore them. *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 53. 64-78. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7796151
104. Antonov A.A. 2023. The relevance of geophysical researches of portals. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 70. 75-89. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.778944>
105. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to prove the existence of hidden Multiverse and to research it. *Annali d'Italia*. 42. 71-85. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7865307
106. Antonov A.A. 2023. Why geophysical researches of portals are necessary. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 105. 83-96.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7779019>
107. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to prove the existence of hidden Multiverse and to research it. *International independent scientific journal*. 49. 23-37.
108. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to discover invisible universes. *Journal of science. Lyon*. 41. 26-38.
109. Antonov A.A. 2023. Geophysical researches of portals will allow to prove the existence of hidden Multiverse and to research it. *Sciences of Europe*. 114. 76-90

110. Antonov A. A. 2024. Astrophysical portals are a source of new knowledge. German International Journal of Modern Science 95. 34- 44.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14609615

111. Antonov A. A. 2024. Scientific value of researches of astrophysical portals. 82. 41-51.

112. Antonov A. A. 2024. The relevance of research on astrophysical portals. Znanstvena misel journal. 98. 35-45

113. Antonov A. A. 2024. Scientific value of researches of astrophysical portals. Sciences of Europe (Praha, Czech Republic).153. 93-106.

114. Antonov A. A. 2024. The existence of astrophysical portals refutes the version of SRT studied in textbooks. Annali d'Italia. 63. 9-19.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14726250

115. Antonov A. A. 2025. Physical Sciences: Astrophysical Portals are a Source of New Knowledge. European Journal of Applied Sciences, Services for Science and Education. UK 13(1). 23-39. DOI:10.14738/aivp.131.18112.